

A Study of Student Buying Behaviour Towards Green Products Through Online Shopping with Special Reference to Lucknow City

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Abstract

The recent development of internet services has led to a shift in consumer purchasing habits from traditional to digital channels. Apart from buying normal goods, consumers are also preferring green products for their basic amenities since they are environmentally friendly. The present research paper aims to examine student buying behaviour towards green products through online shopping. A sample is collected through a structured questionnaire from the female students, and out of the total responses received, only valid responses are taken. This study will focus only on female students. Random sampling is used for collecting samples with respondents belonging to different ages and levels of study. Data is analyzed by using graphs, charts, percentages, etc. This research will provide useful insight to companies for developing new strategies to meet consumer needs and wants, and it will also promote environmentally friendly product options.

Keywords Consumer Behaviour, Green Products, Female Students, Environmentally Friendly.

Introduction

Today's fast-paced world has made time a valuable resource, and the digital sphere has completely changed the way we purchase. Online shopping, which was formerly unusual, has since evolved into a necessary component of our everyday existence due to its incomparable accessibility and convenience. The online marketplace puts an abundance of opportunities at our fingertips, transforming traditional shopping into a quick and easy activity. Products range from groceries to gadgets, fashion to furniture.

The days of having to wait in long checkout lines and squeeze through packed aisles are long gone. Customers may explore a large variety of products, compare prices, read reviews, and make purchases with just a few clicks or taps while at home or on the go. Digital shopping has expanded due to the proliferation of smartphones and high-speed internet connectivity, which have made it possible for people to purchase with formerly unattainable convenience whenever and wherever they choose.

There is the necessity of strong cybersecurity procedures to protect sensitive data is highlighted by security problems including data breaches and online fraud. Transparent return and refund policies are necessary to maintain customer trust, as the absence of in-person engagement with items may also result in differences between expectations and reality.

Online shopping has become a necessary part of daily life in the current digital era, completely changing the way people make purchases of goods and services. Of all the groups that buy online, female college students make up a significant proportion of the consumer base with particular tastes, habits, and difficulties. Businesses have to understand their purchasing habits in order to properly customize their strategies and meet their wants when it comes to online shopping.

Objective of study

1. To identify the factors that influence consumers to buy online.
2. To study consumer's intention to buy green products through online marketing.
3. To find the most demanding products, female students buy them online.

Review of
Literature

Nadia Saleem, Aemen Khalid, Saba Sadiq (2022) "Impact of e-commerce on Consumer Behavior: A Study of Online Shopping Trend among Youth in Lahore City."

The study reveals that social media connectivity significantly influences consumer behaviour and decision-making processes. Consumers prefer both retail and online shopping, with retail shopping being the second preferred medium. E-commerce appeals to consumers due to its greater product range, convenience, and accessibility.

Amandeep Kaur (2013) "E- Shopping -A Changing Shopping Trend."

The rapid development of the Internet and World Wide Web has led to the growth of e-commerce, making it an important marketing channel for businesses. Online retailers must attract customers while providing the right products or services. This study examines factors affecting consumer E-Shopping behaviors, including internet shopping nature, E-commerce websites, online security, privacy, trustworthiness, and online consumer behaviours. It also examines the customer's purchase decision-making process, focusing on information search, reputation, payment security, and post-purchase after-services. Online retailers must carefully consider these factors to improve their performance and attract customers.

Dr. Geetika Tandon Kapoor, Ashish Gupta and Esha Dhawan (2022) "Consumer buying behaviour towards online shopping: an empirical study with reference to Lucknow city, India"

The study found no significant difference in online shopping satisfaction among respondents based on gender, age, or occupation. Time saving was the most important reason for choosing online shopping. Females preferred apparel, while males preferred electronic products. Free home delivery was the most popular factor. However, customers were reluctant to prefer online shopping due to fraud risks and the lack of touch.

Ekta Rastogi, Prof. M.S. Khan, Dr. Doa Naqvi, Mukhtar Ahmad, Firdaus Jahan (2020) "A Comparative study of Online Marketing vs Traditional Marketing pertaining to Green Products and its Role in CSR"

The study suggests that companies should adopt inexperienced marketing to keep up with global trends. This involves educating employees, customers, government agencies, and middlemen about the benefits of inexperienced marketing. Companies should organize workshops, coaching programs, and dialogues about the advantages of inexperienced marketing. Middlemen should be encouraged to promote this concept, and green consumers, industrial consumers, and suppliers should be encouraged to reduce their negative environmental impact. In developing countries like Asia, promoting inexperienced marketing can help businesses produce environmentally responsible products and pressure suppliers to do the same. The study also found that social impact, environmental consciousness, and value significantly influence people's attitudes towards inexperienced products.

Farheen Naz, Judit Olah, Dinu Vasile, Robert Magda (2020) "Green Purchase Behavior of University Students in Hungary: An Empirical Study"

The study explores the consumption patterns and buying behavior of young and educated consumers in Hungary, revealing that factors like Environmental Knowledge, Work-To-Produce (WTP), and Green Product Pricing significantly influence their purchasing decisions. The research suggests that while young consumers are willing to change their behavior for green products, more sustainable practices are needed. The findings can help green businesses modify their marketing strategies.

Methodology Type of research

The type of research to be used is Exploratory and Descriptive in nature.

Sample design

Population: The population in this study is the female student of college residing in Lucknow. Only valid responses are selected from the entire number of responses received.

Sampling technique: Random sampling was used to get information from students in Lucknow, India. The sample students had done online purchasing at least once in their lifetime.

Tools of analysis: Data collected from questionnaires is analyzed using graphs, charts, and percentages. It is intended to assess consumer's intentions to purchase green

products as well as the types of things that female students frequently purchase online.
Sources of data: A descriptive study was done to analyse students' online shopping behaviour towards green products, using both primary and secondary data sources. To gather primary data from respondents, a well-structured questionnaire has been created. Information for the study was gathered from secondary sources, such as books, journals, and websites.

Analysis

Age

By evaluating the data, we can say that the majority of respondents (66%) are between the ages of 19 and 21, 29% are between the ages of 16 and 18, 3% are between the ages of 22 and 24, and 2% are aged 25 and up.

Level of Study

When we consider the level of study of students, we find that the majority of them are undergraduates, accounting for 88% of all respondents, with 8% being postgraduates and 4% studying at another level.

Respondent's online buying habits are analyzed based on whether they shop daily, monthly, occasionally, rarely, or weekly. According to the research, only 2% of all respondents shop online every day, 3% shop weekly, 27% shop monthly, 33% shop rarely, and 35% shop occasionally.

Environmental concerns, health benefits, product quality, cost, social responsibility and other variables all influence respondent's purchasing decisions for green products. According to the data collected from respondents it is analysed that environmental concerns influenced the most respondents to purchase green products (59%), followed by health benefits (54%), product quality (22%), social responsibility (17%), cost (10%) and others (6%).

An environmentally friendly product is one that is made to last its whole life cycle, even when it is no longer functional, and is therefore considered green. From the data it is evaluated that 47% of total respondents agree that green products assist to safeguard the environment, 28% strongly agree, 19% are neutral, 3% disagree with the fact and 3% strongly disagree.

Effectiveness of Online Marketing in Promoting Green Products

The respondents evaluated the efficiency of online marketing in promoting green products using parameters such as Effective, Ineffective, Neutral, Very effective and Very ineffective. According to the data gathered from respondents, 48% believe that online marketing is effective in promoting green products, 25% believe it is very effective, 23% are neutral, 3% say it is ineffective and only 1% believe it is very ineffective.

Main Reasons To Shop Online

Respondent's major motivations for shopping online are convenience, price comparison, product variety, reviews and ratings, time savings, and others. After analyzing the data, it was determined that 49% of all respondents purchase online for time savings, 30% for price comparison, 28% for convenience, 25% for reviews and ratings, 22% for product diversity, and 6% for other reasons.

Most Commonly Purchased Goods

From the data collected it is analysed that a greater number of respondents most commonly purchase clothing and accessories i.e. 79%, 30% of total respondents purchase books and stationery, 27% purchase beauty and cosmetics, 19% purchase groceries, 18% purchase electronics and gadgets, 11% purchase home decor and furnishing, 10% purchase health and wellness products, and 4% purchase other things.

Factors which influence the purchasing decision of consumers are price, product reviews and ratings, brand reputation, free shipping, return policy, social media influence, recommendations from family and friends and others. From the data it is determined that 55% of the total respondents are influenced by the price of the product, 47% by product reviews and ratings, 32% by return policy, 28% by brand reputation, 25% by free shipping, 15% by social media influence, 9% by recommendations from family and friends, and 6% by other factors.

Significance of Research

1. Understanding the factors and products that impact female students enables companies to develop new strategies to meet their needs.
2. By gaining a deeper understanding of female student's preferences, attitudes and decision-making processes, researchers can contribute to the development of strategies and policies that facilitate the widespread adoption of green products.
3. It promotes environmentally friendly product options.

Scope of Study

The study will concentrate on the female population of Lucknow city to provide localized insights into buying behaviour of students towards online shopping.

Conclusion

The study's data analysis revealed that the majority of the female students shop online occasionally. Environmental concerns and health benefits are the two factors that have influenced the female student's decision to purchase green products. It is also found that most of the respondents (47%) agree that green products serve to protect the environment, and only a few of them (3%) disagree. From the information collected, it is analyzed that 48% of the total respondents think that online marketing is effective in promoting green products, and only 1% of the total respondents consider it very ineffective. According to the data obtained by the female students, the main reason to shop online is time savings (49%), followed by price comparison (30%), convenience (28%), reviews and ratings (25%), product variety (22%), and others (6%). The most commonly purchased goods by female students are clothing and accessories. It is analyzed from the data that price (55%) is the biggest factor that can influence the purchasing decisions of consumers. Businesses should consider all these factors in order to satisfy their customers and increase their sales.

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